

CARE Checklist – A rare and unexpected metastasis from lung adenocarcinoma in a male patient: a case report

This checklist was completed according to the CARE (CAse REport) guidelines to ensure comprehensive and transparent reporting of the presented case.

1. Title

Indicates that the study is a case report and describes the main phenomenon: 'An unexpected and rare metastasis from lung adenocarcinoma in a male patient: a case report.'

2. Keywords

Five relevant keywords are provided: Lung adenocarcinoma, Breast metastasis, Male breast, Immunohistochemistry.

3. Abstract

Structured abstract summarizing background, case presentation, and conclusion. Clearly states the rarity and clinical significance of the case.

4. Introduction

Provides background on lung cancer and breast metastases, with references to prevalence and clinical importance of differentiating primary from metastatic lesions.

5. Patient information

A 45-year-old man, chronic smoker, no significant medical or family history. Presents with spinal pain and lymphadenopathy.

6. Clinical findings

Physical examination revealed fixed cervical and supraclavicular lymph nodes and right-sided sciatica.

7. Timeline

Progression from initial diagnosis of lung adenocarcinoma to breast metastasis after 10 months is clearly described.

8. Diagnostic assessment

CT imaging, histopathology, and immunohistochemistry (TTF-1 positive) confirmed lung origin. Differential diagnosis discussed (primary vs. metastatic breast carcinoma).

9. Therapeutic intervention

Cisplatin–vinorelbine chemotherapy and one session of palliative radiotherapy. Partial regression observed after three months.

10. Follow-up and outcomes

Ten months later, breast lesion appeared; confirmed as metastasis. Patient lost to follow-up thereafter.

11. Discussion

Integrates literature review, diagnostic challenges, and relevance of immunohistochemistry. Compares findings with published cases.

12. Patient perspective

Not reported (patient lost to follow-up).

13. Informed consent

Written informed consent for publication of clinical details and images was obtained from the patient.

14. Conclusion

Highlights the rarity of breast metastasis from lung adenocarcinoma in men and emphasizes accurate diagnosis for proper management.

15. References

Appropriate citations provided, including relevant literature on similar cases and diagnostic considerations.

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According to the CARE guidelines (www.care-statement.org).